

Oral Myiasis: A Case Report

Chidambar Siddegowda#1, Monika Ganvir*2

#Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, ACPM Dental College, India

*Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College, India

Received: May 03, 2025

Accepted: Jun 03, 2025

Published: Jun 05, 2025

Abstract—Myiasis is the infestation of living vertebrates by the larvae of dipterous flies. Oral myiasis is rare and mostly occurs in patients with poor oral hygiene or predisposing factors. This case report describes a 60-year-old mentally disabled female with gingival myiasis successfully treated by mechanical removal of larvae and local irrigation.

Keywords—Oral myiasis, larvae, gingival swelling, turpentine oil, infestation

I. Introduction

The term myiasis, derived from the Greek word *myia* meaning fly, was coined by Hope in 1840 [1]. Myiasis is the infestation of living vertebrates by the larvae (maggots) of dipterous (two-winged) flies [1]. Zumpt defined it as the infestation of live human and vertebrate animals with dipterous larvae, which for a period feed on the host's dead or living tissue, liquid body substances, or ingested food.

Cases of myiasis have been reported in epileptic patients with lacerated lips following seizures, children with incompetent lips and thumb sucking habits, patients with advanced periodontal disease, at tooth extraction sites, in fungating carcinoma of the buccal mucosa, and in tetanus patients with the mouth propped open [1]. Oral myiasis has also occurred as a nosocomial infection in immobile, severely ill individuals and as a superimposed infection in fractured mandibles. However, gingival myiasis has been reported in healthy individuals with acceptable oral hygiene [1].

II. Case Report

A 60-year-old female with mental disability was referred to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery with a complaint of gingival swelling. There was no history of pain. Family and medical history were non-significant.

Fig. 1—Appearance of patient at presentation.

Extraoral examination revealed mild swelling over the right mid-face region (Fig. 1). Right and left submandibular lymph nodes were palpable. Intraorally, swelling was noted on the anterior maxillary region on both labial and palatal sides along with poor oral hygiene. An erythematous gingival swelling was found in relation to teeth 13, 12, 11, 21, 22, and 23. The swelling showed multiple small orifices between the gingival surface and teeth 13, 12, and 11 through which live maggots were seen emerging (Fig. 2). A layer of blood clot covered teeth 21 and 22. The associated teeth had no caries and were vital.

Fig. 2—Swollen gingiva with maggots emerging from small orifices on the lesion surface.

Hematologic investigations were within normal limits. The treatment plan included mechanical removal of the maggots. Maggots visible on the surface were removed using surgical forceps. Remaining larvae deep in the lesion were induced to emerge by applying turpentine oil. Since the associated teeth were intact and no other dental infections were present, causes such as dentoalveolar abscess and pyogenic granuloma were excluded. A diagnosis of gingival myiasis was confirmed. Poor oral hygiene and lack of awareness were considered predisposing factors.

Fig. 3—Collected maggots after removal from the lesion.

Collected larvae displayed a spiral form and varied in size from 5 to 10 mm (Fig. 3). After complete removal, the lesion was irrigated with normal saline and betadine solution. Complete prophylaxis was carried out.

Post-procedure instructions included the use of warm saline rinses until lesion resolution and scheduling follow-up visits. One week after treatment, there was reduced gingival erythema and swelling. Complete resolution was observed after approximately two weeks.

III. Discussion

Several species cause oral myiasis depending on geographic distribution of dipterous flies. Oral myiasis is a rare condition mostly reported in tropical and developing countries [2]. Infestation occurs either by accidental direct inoculation of larvae by flies or ingestion of infected materials. Most reported cases involve lesions in the anterior oral cavity suggesting direct inoculation [4]. The present case involved anterior maxillary gingiva consistent with this mode of infestation.

Fernandes et al. identified *Cochliomyia hominivorax* as the predominant agent of human myiasis in the New World, including oral myiasis in Brazil [2]. These larvae are obligatory parasites that grow on healthy tissue and destroy it [2].

Oral myiasis can be primary or secondary to nasal involvement, with larvae potentially invading paranasal sinuses or palate. Rarely, infestation occurs in eyes, nose, paranasal sinuses, urogenital tract, or rectum [5]. Predisposing factors include poor oral hygiene, incompetent lips, halitosis, and compromised host defenses.

Treatment involves mechanical removal of larvae and surgical debridement under local anesthesia. Application of irritating solutions such as turpentine oil facilitates larval emergence, followed by irrigation with warm saline [4]. There are no effective chemotherapeutic agents currently available [3]. Prevention focuses on good oral hygiene, especially in debilitated or immobile patients [2].

IV. Conclusion

Oral myiasis is a rare but potentially serious condition that primarily affects individuals with poor oral hygiene or compromised health status. Early diagnosis and prompt mechanical removal of larvae, combined with proper oral hygiene and supportive care, are essential for successful treatment and prevention of complications. Increased awareness among healthcare providers and caregivers is important for timely management of such cases.

Acknowledgment

The authors wish to thank the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery staff for their support in managing this case.

References

- [1] A. P. Bhatt and A. Jayakrishnan, "Oral myiasis: a case report," *Int. J. Paediatr. Dent.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 67–70, Mar. 2000.
- [2] M. C. Ribeiro et al., "Oral myiasis in an elderly patient," *Gerodontology*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. e1136–e1139, Jun. 2012.
- [3] R. Gutta, L. Vega, and P. J. Louis, "Traumatic wound myiasis: an unusual finding in maxillofacial trauma," *J. Oral Maxillofac. Surg.*, vol. 65, no. 10, pp. 2083–2086, Oct. 2007.
- [4] E. B. Droma et al., "Oral myiasis: a case report and literature review," *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol. Endod.*, vol. 103, no. 1, pp. 92–96, Jan. 2007.
- [5] M. Gursel et al., "A rare case of gingival myiasis caused by diptera (Calliphoridae)," *J. Clin. Periodontol.*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 777–780, Aug. 2002.